

Table 2. Frequency of restorers, partial restorers, and maintainers for V20 A in red- and white-kernel rice varieties. Kerala, India. 1994-95.

Varietal group	Lines (no.)	Restorers	Partial restorers	Maintainers
Red kernel	17	0 (0) ^a	7 (41.2)	10 (58.8)
White kernel	21	6 (28.6)	8 (38.0)	7 (33.4)

^aFigures in parentheses indicate percentages.

IKI stain. Three panicles each from the same plant were bagged before flowering to facilitate selfing. Spikelet fertility was calculated as percentage of filled grains. Hybrids showing >80% pollen and spikelet fertility were classified as fertile, those with 100% pollen and spikelet sterility were considered sterile, and the rest were classified as partially fertile. Accordingly, the male

parents were classified as restorers, maintainers, and partial restorers (Tables 1 and 2). Among the 43 varieties tested, 18 were effective maintainers, 7 effective restorers, and 16 partial restorers. The response of two varieties depended on the female parent used (maintainer/restorer for one CMS line and partial restorer for the other), indicating the influence of the genetic background of

Machhapuchhre 3 (MP3), the first rice variety developed through a participatory plant breeding approach released for mid to high altitudes of Nepal

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Adoption rates for exotic rice varieties in the eastern and western hills of Nepal are reported to be 10-11%. Seven F₅ bulks representing three crosses—Fuji 102/CD, K332/NR10157-2B-2, and Stejarec 45/CD—were given to expert farmers identified through a village workshop. They were asked to grow and manage the new entries along with their local variety in the same way. The participatory plant breeding (PPB) system included a farm walk to different trial sites, preference ranking, measurement of farmers' managed yield data, postharvest evaluations by women farmers, and monitoring of varietal spread. Farmer-selected lines were also included in national yield trials to satisfy variety release require-

Comparison of the means of top five conventionally bred varieties (CBVs) with that of Machhapuchhre 3.

ments. In contrast to conventional breeding practices, most farmers grew the new entries in medium fertility conditions. A few farmers chose plots they regarded as problematic. The overall strategy emphasized risk aversion and expanding successful lines to better fields. Decisions on retaining or rejecting any rice entry was largely taken after women farmers thoroughly evaluated postharvest traits, such as white grain color along with aroma, softness of cooked rice, and ability to expand and remain dry after cooking. Focused group discussion with the farmers revealed that grain yield alone did not influence farmers' decision of adopting and spreading MP3 although the variety yielded well

the female parent on the nuclear gene expression of the male parent. The frequency of maintainers and partial restorers was very high among the red-kernel rice varieties, but practically nil among complete restorers. Hybrids with the red-kernel Kerala rice varieties when used as male parents were either sterile or partially fertile, but none was completely fertile. The sterile hybrids are being back-crossed with some of the identified maintainers (PTB39, PTB52, MO 4, MO 8, etc.) to develop locally adaptable CMS lines with red kernels for future use in hybrid rice development. The fertile hybrids are being assessed for their heterosis and adaptability under different conditions. ■

even in the formal varietal trials (see figure). Macchhapuchhre 3 has been officially released for altitudes between 1400 and 2000 m of western Nepal, on 14 Jul 1996, or less than 8 yr from the initial crossing in autumn 1988. This is the first recorded example of a successful variety developed by decentralized selection of segregating material through PPB drawing active participation of expert farmers. Experience from this experiment suggests that the PPB approach is a cost-effective and suitable method for developing farmers' need-based crop varieties. ■

Breeding of Zi-Biao S line, the indica photothermosensitive genic male sterile line with recessive purple leaf marker

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We developed two photothermosensitive genic male sterile lines (PTGMS) with recessive purple leaf marker, Zi-Biao S-1 and Zi-Biao S-2, to eliminate seed contamination that may result from incomplete male sterility of PTGMS lines in a two-line, hybrid rice seed production system.